

SIMULATING FLUID FLOW WITHIN CORONARY ARTERIES USING PARALLELIZED SPARSE LATTICE BOLZTMANN METHOD

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Abstract:

In clinical diagnostics of the coronary artery stenosis, the state of fluid flow is analyzed by invasively measuring fractional flow reserve (FFR). However, a more detailed hemodynamic evaluation of the flow and its spatial and temporal distribution may be more insightful for the diagnostics. A realistic simulation of blood flow inside the patient-specific coronary artery could be a better alternative to the invasive measurement of FFR. In this study, lattice Boltzmann (LB) method was used for the simulations of fluid flow through complex geometries of human coronary arteries. For such complex geometries, a large number of nodes in the LB mesh are denoted as fixed and this imposes large computational and memory requirements that are unnecessary. In this study, this standard approach is improved by using a sparse domain that includes the fluid nodes and its closest fixed (solid) nodes. This way, the amount of required memory resources is significantly reduced. During implementation, the software is parallelized to execute on a GPU (graphics processing unit) device, ensuring that the amount of computational time needed for the execution of the simulation is also significantly reduced. The software presented in this paper provides a valuable tool that can be used in clinical practice for quick assessment of the state of the arteries and provide fast quantitative information about fluid flow that could be very useful for medical diagnostics and decision-making.

Key words: computational fluid dynamics, lattice Boltzmann method, sparse solver, parallelization, GPU device

1. Introduction

Coronary arteries are important part of the human cardiovascular system and also the one with very high risk of development of stenosis. In clinical diagnostics, the state of fluid flow through the coronary arteries is analyzed by invasively measuring fractional flow reserve (FFR) [1]. The obtained value helps the clinician to determine whether the stenosis in the considered artery is

hemodynamically significant or not. However, a more detailed hemodynamic evaluation of the flow and its spatial and temporal distribution may be even more insightful for the diagnostics. A realistic simulation of blood flow inside the patient-specific coronary artery could be a better alternative to the invasive measurement of FFR.

There are several numerical methods within computational fluid dynamics (CFD) that are capable of simulating the fluid flow. They can be divided to methods that observe the fluid as a continuum (e.g. finite element method – FEM) and discrete methods that observe the fluid as a set of particles (e.g. Dissipative Particle Dynamics – DPD or lattice Boltzmann (LB) method). In this study, the LB method was adapted for the simulations of fluid flow through complex geometries of human coronary arteries. One of the main advantages of this method is its discrete nature that enables easy parallelization of the software on GPU (graphics processing unit) devices, that was already performed in literature [2,3]. The capabilities of this method to simulate many complex phenomena in biomedicine have already been demonstrated in literature. LB method was used to simulate the motion of otoconia particles within the semicircular canals of the inner ear [4,5], the motion of circulating tumor cells within the microfluidic chips [6,7] etc.

LB method has also been used in literature to study the flow through complex domains, including flow through porous media [8], transient flow of fully detailed production-level passenger and heavy-duty vehicles [9] and coronary arteries [10]. LB method uses a fixed Cartesian mesh of nodes within the simulations. The standard approach when simulating flow through complex domains is to use bounce-back boundary condition [11] for the fixed (solid) nodes. However, for very complex geometries, this means that a large number of nodes in the LB mesh need to be denoted as fixed and this imposes large computational and memory requirements that are unnecessary. In this study, the mentioned standard approach is improved by using a sparse domain that includes the fluid nodes and its closest fixed (solid) nodes. This way, the amount of memory resources is significantly reduced. During implementation, the software based on LB method is parallelized to execute on a GPU device, ensuring that the amount of computational time needed for the execution of the simulation is also significantly reduced.

The paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, the LB method and the sparse implementation are presented. Section 3 presents the results of the parallelization procedure and results of the blood flow simulation for a particular patient. Section 4 concludes the paper.

2. Materials and Methods

This Section briefly lists the basic equations of the LB method in Subsection 2.1 and presents the sparse implementation and parallelization approach in Subsection 2.2.

2.1 Equations of the LB method

The basic quantity within the equations of LB method is the distribution function f . This function represents a probability for a LB fictitious particle to be moving along the predefined directions. The equation that represents the entire LB numerical scheme is most commonly separated into two steps – collision step and propagation step that can be described using following equations:

$$\bar{f}_i^{out}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \bar{f}_i^{in}(\mathbf{x}, t) - \frac{1}{\bar{\tau}} (\bar{f}_i^{in}(\mathbf{x}, t) - f_i^{(0)}(\rho, \mathbf{u})), \quad (1)$$

$$\bar{f}_i^{in}(\mathbf{x} + \bar{\xi}_i, t + 1) = \bar{f}_i^{out}(\mathbf{x}, t), \quad (2)$$

where the superscripts in and out denote the discretized values of the distribution function before and after collision, respectively. In the above equation, $\bar{\tau}$ represents the relaxation time and $\bar{\xi}_i$

represent vectors defining the abscissae of the lattice structure. The abscissae for lattice structure that is used for three-dimensional isothermal flow of incompressible fluid in this study (denoted by D3Q27) are shown in Figure 1. The quantity $f_i^{(0)}$ is the equilibrium distribution function. Details of the derivation procedure of LB method can be found in literature [12,13].

Macroscopic quantities (pressure, velocity and wall shear stress) are calculated in terms of the distribution function, using the following equations:

$$p = c_s^2 \sum_i \bar{f}_i, \quad (3)$$

$$\bar{\mathbf{u}} = \frac{1}{\rho} \sum_i \bar{\xi}_i \bar{f}_i, \quad (4)$$

$$\tau_i = -\frac{\mu}{c_s^2 \bar{\tau} \rho} (\bar{f}_j - f_j^{(0)}) \bar{\xi}_{jk} n_k (\bar{\xi}_{ji} - \bar{\xi}_{jl} n_l), \quad (5)$$

In above equations c_s represents the constant related to the LB method and lattice structure. For the structure D3Q27 used in this paper, this constant is equal to $c_s^2 = 1/3$.

Bounce-back boundary condition is very simple for implementation and that is one of the reasons for its wide popularity. It is most commonly applied when solving problems with complex boundaries, when certain nodes of the mesh should be marked as solid nodes, i.e. as the wall. In all such nodes the components of the distribution function are not evaluated in the same way as in the rest of the nodes.

If the direction opposite to the direction i in the mesh is denoted by $opp(i)$, the components of the distribution function are evaluated using the following expression:

$$\bar{f}_i = \bar{f}_{opp(i)}, \quad (6)$$

When the simulations of fluid flow are performed, it is most common to impose the Dirichlet boundary conditions, i.e. to define the values of velocity and pressure. In LB method, for this purpose the regularized method [14] is used. Using this approach, the missing components of the distribution function coming from the inlet or outlet are calculated using the predefined values of velocity or pressure.

Fig. 1. Lattice structure D3Q27 with denoted indices of the neighboring nodes within the index list for sparse implementation

2.2 Implementation of the sparse LB method

In a standard LB implementation, the entire domain is mapped on a structured grid and the LB mesh is divided along the three axes. LB nodes and their neighbors are accessed according to their indices along the three axes. The coordinates of the neighbors for the lattice structure D3Q27 considered in this study are calculated using the coordinate system shown in Figure 1. The box coordinates are -1 and 1 along all the three axes. In the sparse implementation, the entire domain is mapped on an unstructured grid. This practically means that not all neighbors will be accessible, since nodes that are marked as solid are completely eliminated. Each fluid node is numbered with a unique index and for each node an index list is created that consists of the indices of the neighboring fluid nodes. This sparse approach was proposed in literature [15]. Within this study, the index list for the sparse representation is implemented with an array with 26 integers (the 27th element of the D3Q27 structure is the considered node itself). The indices of the neighboring nodes for one node of the considered lattice structure are shown in Figure 1. In case that neighboring node is solid (and hence nonexistent) the appropriate value in the array is -1. Within the propagation step, instead of accessing the neighboring elements with $\tilde{f}_i^{in}(\mathbf{x} + \tilde{\xi}_i, t + 1)$, they are accessed by their indices from the index list $\tilde{f}_i^{in}(n(\mathbf{x}, i), t + 1)$.

GPU device is an upgraded version of NVIDIA graphics cards that can be used for general purpose computing. CUDA architecture (Compute Unified Device Architecture) developed by NVIDIA was used within this study to parallelize the software based on sparse LB method. A similar approach already presented in literature [2] is used within this study, but the propagation step is changed according to the previously mentioned index list. During the initialization of data, the entire domain from the standard LB mesh is transversed in order to calculate the number of fluid neighbors for each LB node. All nodes containing at least one fluid node are included in the sparse model and assigned a unique ID. Then the index lists are created for all nodes. This data is transferred to the memory of the GPU device and then the execution of the loop of iterations (performing the collision and propagation steps) is performed on the GPU until the defined number of iterations is reached.

3. Results

The geometry of the coronary artery was obtained within the European project SMARTool. The 0.3 mm DICOM images were obtained within clinical CT angiography (CTA) examination of a coronary artery of the considered patient. The geometry was extracted using the Mimics commercial software (Materialise NV, Leuven, Belgium) and the STL (stereolithography) file containing triangularized surface geometry was generated. The obtained geometry for the considered patient is shown in Figure 2(a). Then, the geometry was placed within the box domain necessary for the LB method and the domain is voxelized, to determine the nodes inside the STL geometry (that are marked as fluid nodes) and those outside the geometry (that are marked as solid nodes). The voxelized model with all nodes is shown in Figure 2(b). The voxelized model used within the sparse implementation is shown in Figure 2(c). As already mentioned in Section 2.2, here only the nodes with at least one fluid neighboring node are included in the sparse model. Thus, there is only one layer of bounce-back nodes, representing the arterial wall. In these nodes the velocity will be equal to zero, like it is usually defined in simulations using standard CFD methods like FEM.

The benefits of the parallelization are demonstrated by measuring the obtained speed up. The speed up was calculated for two architectures – a PC computer with good graphics card and a computer cluster with high-end GPU device. The PC configuration consists of an Intel Core i7 processor, at 3.00 GHz with 32 GB RAM memory and NVIDIA GeForce RTX 2080 Ti graphics card and is denoted as Configuration#1. The cluster configuration consists of an Intel Xeon Gold

6148 (Skylake) processor at 2.4 GHz with 16 GB RAM memory and NVIDIA Tesla V100 GPU device and is denoted as Configuration#2. The execution time of the sequential and parallel versions of the software implementation of sparse LB method are compared and the obtained values of speedup are shown in Figure 3. For both configurations, the speedup increases with the number of nodes until the final value is reached. This final value is determined by the characteristics of the GPU device, which is obvious from the fact that the speedup with high-end GPU device of configuration#2 is much greater than the speedup with a graphics card of a PC computer.

Fig. 2. The geometry of coronary artery. (a) STL geometry extracted from clinical data; (b) Full voxelized model; (c) Sparse voxelized model; blue color denotes fluid nodes, green color denotes solid (bounce-back) nodes

Fig. 3. Speedup obtained for the sparse implementation of LB method

In order to determine which is the optimal number of nodes in LB mesh that should be used for simulations, a mesh independence study was conducted and the results are shown in Table 1. The parameter that was analyzed is the maximum fluid velocity. Both the number of nodes in the sparse model and the number of nodes that would be needed for the equivalent full model are given in Table 1. As it can be seen, less than 5% difference in calculated fluid velocity is obtained with around 380.000 nodes for the sparse model. If the same simulation were to be performed with the standard full voxelized mesh, then almost 9.5 million nodes would be needed for the simulation. Such simulation would be impossible on a single GPU device, due to the large memory requirements. This demonstrates the need to use sparse LB method for the simulations of complex domains, such as coronary arteries.

Number of nodes – sparse model	Number of nodes – full model	Maximum velocity [mm/s]
7369	56320	321.799
16827	204085	471.579
26869	384300	481.256
66780	1213960	763.267
90237	1767500	867.698
133435	2806040	978.428
215488	4910360	1194.990
313782	7571880	1334.126
381043	9401568	1376.121

Table 1. Results of the mesh independence study

Results of the LB simulation are shown in Figure 4. During the simulation, the results from the voxelized model are interpolated on the STL geometry for the post-processing purposes. The velocity streamlines are shown in Figure 4(a), pressure distribution is shown in Figure 4(b) and the WSS distribution is shown in Figure 4(c). When the presented results are compared with the results obtained using PakF software based on FEM [16], using the same simulation setup, the standard error for the analyzed quantities is 0.098% for velocity, 0.17% for WSS and 0.3% for pressure.

Fig. 4. Results of the fluid flow simulation for the considered patient. (a) Velocity streamlines, units are [mm/s]; (b) Pressure distribution, units are [Pa]; (c) WSS distribution, units are [dyne/cm²]

4. Conclusions

Complex numerical simulations of blood flow in coronary arteries are very demanding, both from the aspect of memory consumption and the execution time. The execution time of an LB simulation can be significantly reduced by using parallelization techniques and executing the software on a GPU device. However, LB meshes that can be saved and processed within the memory of a single GPU are sometimes too coarse for precise and more detailed analysis of the blood flow in smaller compartments of a vessel with complex geometry, like it is a coronary artery. In these cases it is necessary to perform simulations on a very fine mesh grid that contains millions of nodes. The sparse parallel implementation of LB method presented in this study is a valuable alternative that can provide accurate results quickly. The overall number of nodes can be reduced from several million nodes to less than a million, by excluding the unnecessary solid nodes. On a standard PC computer with a high performance graphics card, like NVIDIA GeForce RTX 2080 Ti, the execution time of steady-state blood flow simulation is less than 1 minute (25 seconds), while a simulation of one complete cardiac cycle executes in around 4 minutes. The presented software provides a valuable tool that can be used in clinical practice for quick assessment of the state of the arteries and provide fast quantitative information about fluid flow that could be very useful for medical diagnostics and decision-making.

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